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Body-centered cubic phase stability in cobalt-free refractory high-entropy alloys

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ABSTRACT

Cobalt-free refractory high-entropy alloys (RHEAs) are strong contenders for structural materials in nuclear reactors because they do not exhibit cobalt activity under irradiation. The mechanical properties and thermal stability of RHEAs are primarily attributed to the solid solution phase, which is essentially the body-centered cubic (BCC) phase. The BCC phase formation rules thus became the basic criterion in the compositional design of RHEAs. In this paper, the BCC phase formation rules in cobalt-free RHEAs were determined via the calculation of six semiempirical parameters, namely, the entropy of mixing, enthalpy of mixing, atomic size difference, Ω -parameter, d-orbital energy level and valence electron concentration. The mixing enthalpy and atomic size differences are more effective than other semiempirical parameters for predicting BCC phase stability in cobalt-free RHEAs. The presence of aluminum is found to cause a notable alteration in the range of phase stability in cobalt-free RHEAs.

Introduction

Since the concept of equiatomic or near-equiatomic multicomponent alloys comprising four or more metallic elements was proposed, high-entropy alloys (HEAs) have attracted significant interest [1–3]. Compared to those of conventional metallic materials such as steels [4,5], copper alloys [6,7], tungsten alloys [8] and niobium alloys [9], the superior comprehensive mechanical properties of HEAs [10–13], especially their stable properties under extreme environments [14–18], have made them one of the most promising structural materials for next-generation nuclear energy systems [14]. For instance, the disordered solid solution phase still remained in a CrFeCoNi alloy under 1250 keV electron irradiation for up to 1 dpa at 673 K, and no phase separation or decomposition was detected [19]. It was reported that the Al_xCoCrFeNi alloy system exhibited significantly lower irradiation-induced volume swelling than did conventional materials under 3 MeV Au-ion irradiation [20]. However, cobalt activation due to neutron irradiation makes Co-containing HEAs unsuitable for nuclear engineering applications [21,22]. Refractory HEAs (RHEAs) are a type of HEA that contains

multiple transition elements with high melting points, such as Nb, Mo, Ta, W, Hf, V, Zr and Ti, as their main components can meet high-temperature stability and Co-free requirements [23–25].

The mechanical properties of RHEAs can be optimized by adjusting the phase components and microstructures through the selection of alloy systems and changing alloying elements [26]. However, the final phase structures can often be detected only after manufacturing due to the complex composition of RHEAs, which undoubtedly adds to the significant cost of the study. During the last decade, several semiempirical phase formation rules, such as the entropy of mixing (ΔS_{mix}), enthalpy of mixing (ΔH_{mix}), atomic size difference (δ) and Ω parameter, have been proposed to improve HEA design [27,28]. It is easy to obtain a solid solution phase in HEAs when $12 \leq \Delta S_{mix} \leq 17.5 \text{ J}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$, $-15 \leq \Delta H_{mix} \leq 5 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$, $\delta \leq 6.6$ and $\Omega \geq 1.1$ [27,28]. With the development of related research, new parameters related to valence electrons, such as the d-orbital energy level ($\bar{M}d$) and valence electron concentration (VEC), have been proposed to further improve the phase formation rules [29,30]. These six parameters are effective at predicting the phase formation of some HEAs. Nevertheless, the feasibility of phase prediction

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for RHEAs still needs further study.

In this work, multicomponent systems of Co-free RHEAs reported in the literature were collected, and the corresponding parameters, including ΔS_{mix} , ΔH_{mix} , Ω , δ , \overline{Md} and VEC , were calculated. Solid solution phase formation rules for Co-free RHEAs were proposed based on composition design theory, which can be used for nuclear engineering applications. The effect of Al in Co-free RHEAs on BCC phase formation was studied.

Methods

Data collection

The various multicomponent systems of Co-free RHEAs were summarized by collecting alloy systems in previous reports [31–103]. The compositions of Co-free RHEAs and the calculated values of the six parameters ΔS_{mix} , ΔH_{mix} , Ω , δ , \overline{Md} and VEC are listed in Table A1. The phase components of Co-free RHEAs were characterized under as-cast/homogenized/recrystallized conditions.

Composition design theory

The four semiempirical parameters ΔS_{mix} , ΔH_{mix} , Ω , and δ are defined by the following equations [27,28,104]:

$$\Delta S_{mix} = -R \sum_{i=1}^n C_i \ln C_i \quad (1)$$

where C_i is the atomic fraction of the i -th element, $R = 8.314 \text{ JK}^{-1} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$ is the gas constant, and

$$\Delta H_{mix} = \sum_{i=1, i \neq j}^n \Omega_{ij} C_i C_j \quad (2)$$

where the i -th element is distinct from the j -th element; $\Omega = 4\Delta H_{AB}^{mix}$ is the enthalpy of mixing between the interacting elements i and j ; and

$$\delta = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1, i \neq j}^n C_i (1 - r_i/\bar{r})^2}, \quad (3)$$

where r_i is the atomic radius of the i th element and the average atomic radius \bar{r} is defined as $\bar{r} = \sum_{i=1}^n c_i r_i$. Ω is a parameter that takes into account the combined effects of ΔS_{mix} and ΔH_{mix} and is expressed as follows:

$$\Omega = \frac{T_m \Delta S_{mix}}{|\Delta H_{mix}|}, \quad (4)$$

where T_m is the melting temperature of the multicomponent alloy. Two other d-electron-related parameters, \overline{Md} and VEC , were also adopted, which were proposed as [29,30,105]:

$$\overline{Md} = \sum_{i=1}^n C_i (Md)_i, \quad (5)$$

$$VEC = \sum_{i=1}^n C_i (VEC)_i, \quad (6)$$

where $(Md)_i$ and $(VEC)_i$ are the d-orbital energy level and VEC of the i -th element, respectively. It is important to note that the alloying elements M exhibit different Md values when considering the structures of various solvent elements X due to the influence of electronegativity and the atomic radius of both solute and solvent elements [106,107]. Therefore, the Md values of the alloying elements in FCC Ni, BCC Fe and BCC Cr are all considered to verify the feasibility of each structure in Co-free RHEAs; these values are listed in Table 1 [108,109].

Table 1

Md values of the alloying elements in FCC Ni, BCC Fe and BCC Cr.

Alloying element	Md value in FCC Ni	Md value in BCC Fe	Md value in BCC Cr
Ti	2.271	2.497	2.87
V	1.543	1.61	1.998
Cr	1.142	1.059	1.301
Mn	0.957	0.854	0.752
Fe	0.858	0.825	0.694
Co	0.777	0.755	0.658
Ni	0.717	0.661	0.213
Cu	0.615	0.637	−0.346
Zr	2.944	3.074	3.359
Nb	2.117	2.335	2.662
Mo	1.55	1.663	1.968
Hf	3.02	3.159	4.518
Ta	2.224	2.486	3.605
W	1.655	1.836	2.768
Al	1.9	1.034	1.034

Results

The individual parameter values of phases in RHEAs

The effects of parameters \overline{Md} in FCC Ni, \overline{Md} in BCC Fe, \overline{Md} in BCC Cr, VEC , ΔS_{mix} , ΔH_{mix} , Ω and δ on the stability of various phases in Co-free RHEAs are clearly plotted in Fig. 1. All four phases, bulk metallic glass (BMG), intermetallic (IM), BCC and intermetallic mixed phase (BCC + IM) and the BCC phase, have different \overline{Md} values for FCC Ni, BCC Fe and BCC Cr, respectively. \overline{Md} in FCC Ni has the lowest values, and the highest values are in BCC Fe; \overline{Md} in BCC Cr is between the former two. It can be clearly seen from Fig. 1a, b and c that \overline{Md} for BMG and IM are relatively low, and the BCC + IM phase and BCC phase are distributed in wide ranges that almost cover the ranges of BMG and IM. Conversely, the VEC s for BMG and IM had relatively greater values than did those for the BCC + IM phase and BCC phase. BMGs and IMs are prone to form when the VEC is greater than 5.67. However, describing the difference between these four phases in terms of ΔS_{mix} is difficult because their ranges overlap. Like \overline{Md} , ΔH_{mix} is relatively high for the BCC phase and low for the BMG and IM phases. A clear phase boundary of $-18.78 \text{ kJ} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$ in terms of ΔH_{mix} between the BMG and BCC phases can be observed in Fig. 1f. As the Ω parameter is a function of ΔS_{mix} and ΔH_{mix} , BMG and IM are more stable when Ω is lower than 1.65. It is noteworthy that the distribution range of the BCC phase is significantly different from that of the BMG and IM phases in terms of δ . Only the BCC + IM phase forms when δ is in the range of 7.63%—9.25%, and the BMG and IM phases form when δ is greater than 9.25. As shown in Fig. 1, ΔH_{mix} and δ have the most significant effects on the formation of the solid solution phase and BMG. However, the distribution ranges of the BCC + IM phase and BCC phase of the BMG and IM phases always overlap and are difficult to distinguish. Further research is required for BMG and IM due to a lack of data.

Effect of various parameters on BCC-structured RHEAs

The excellent mechanical properties of RHEAs are mainly attributed to the solid solution phase, and the solid solution phase formation rules are critical for phase prediction in RHEAs [24,110]. Therefore, in the following sections, only the BCC + IM phase and BCC phase are discussed. It is noted that in Table A1, a large number of RHEAs contain the nontransition metal Al. Al, as an extra element, can significantly impact the properties of RHEAs and is often used to adjust phase components and structure [111,112]. Therefore, there are two groups of Co-free RHEAs based on whether they contain Al.

The effects of the individual parameters on the solid solution phase stability in the two groups of Co-RHEAs are shown in Fig. 2. As shown in

Fig. 1. The effect of \overline{M}_d for alloying elements in FCC Ni (a), BCC Fe (b) and BCC Cr (c), VEC (d), ΔS_{mix} (e), ΔH_{mix} (f), Ω (g) and δ (h) on phase stability in RHEAs.

Fig. 2a, b and c, \overline{M}_d in three different structures are unable to distinguish between the BCC phase and mixed phase of two groups of Co-free RHEAs. The distribution ranges of the mixed phase and BCC phase overlap with each other for both VEC and ΔS_{mix} , irrespective of the presence of Al. In terms of ΔH_{mix} , as illustrated in Fig. 2f, Al-containing RHEAs generally have more negative values than Al-free RHEAs, and the mixed phase of Al-containing RHEAs has even more negative values than the BCC phase. Notably, these two alloy systems contain the FCC structural element Ni, and the ΔH_{mix} of RHEAs can reach a very negative value with the addition of Ni, thus forming a mixed phase. As $|\Delta H_{mix}|$ increases and Ω decreases, the inverse relationship between Ω and ΔH_{mix} is well established, as shown in Fig. 2g. Different distributions of δ can be found between the mixed phase and the BCC phase within the two groups of RHEAs. The mixed phase had higher δ values than did the BCC phase. However, it is still impossible to describe the solid solution formation rules for Co-free RHEAs when only one parameter is considered, regardless of the presence of Al.

Combined effect of parameters on BCC-structured RHEAs

Effect of the atomic size difference on the phase stability of Co-free RHEAs

Numerous studies have reported that δ plays an important role in the phase prediction of HEAs [28,113,114]. It is important to note that δ cannot be utilized as a single parameter for predicting phase formation. Therefore, the distributions of δ superimposed on the valence electron-related parameters are plotted in Fig. 3. Interestingly, the BCC phase of the two Co-free RHEAs is distributed in the upper-right and lower-left regions of the \overline{M}_d and δ plots, as shown in Fig. 3a, b and c. Compared with the other two \overline{M}_d plots, the BCC + IM phase in the Al-containing RHEAs is distributed in a region similar to that of the Al-free RHEAs when \overline{M}_d is calculated based on FCC Ni, and the clear solid solution formation rules cannot be defined from the random distribution. For \overline{M}_d in BCC Fe and Cr, the BCC + IM phase of the Al-containing RHEAs is distributed between these two regions, while the majority of the BCC + IM phase of the Al-free RHEAs is located in the region with both high \overline{M}_d and high δ values. The Co-free RHEAs located in the upper-right region

Fig. 2. Effect of \overline{M}_d for FCC Ni (a), BCC Fe (b), BCC Cr (c), VEC (d), ΔS_{mix} (e), ΔH_{mix} (f), Ω (g) and δ (h) on the phase stability of BCC-structured RHEAs.

mainly consist of a combination of 3d, 4d and 5d transition metals, resulting in high δ values. With the additions of high- \overline{M}_d -value elements, Hf and Zr, the Co-free RHEAs show high \overline{M}_d values. However, if the δ values of Al-free and Al-containing RHEAs exceed 7.63 % and 6.28 %, respectively, IM phases will form in Co-free RHEAs. The VEC in Fig. 3d displays a comparable distribution of the BCC phase in Al-free RHEAs, whereas a distinct two-part distribution is not found in Al-containing RHEAs with a BCC phase. Likewise, if the Co-free RHEAs contain low VEC elements such as Hf and Zr, they are located in the lower-right region. With the addition of the nontransition metal Al, the VEC values of Co-free RHEAs significantly decrease since Al has a lower VEC than transition metals.

The effects of δ superimposed on ΔS_{mix} , ΔH_{mix} and Ω are shown in Fig. 4. Like for the effect of a single ΔS_{mix} , the $\Delta S_{mix} - \delta$ plot still displays a random distribution of phase stability. The mixed and BCC phases are divided into four parts based on whether the Co-free RHEAs contained Al when ΔH_{mix} and δ are combined. Co-free RHEAs without Al are prone to form a solid solution phase when $-6.50 \leq \Delta H_{mix} \leq 2.72 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ and $\delta \leq 7.63 \%$, and the range is changed to $-16.84 \leq \Delta H_{mix} \leq -3.99$

$\text{kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ and $\delta \leq 6.28 \%$ with the addition of Al. Although there is some overlap between these four regions, it is possible to describe simple rules for the formation of solid solution phases in Co-free RHEAs. The two mixed-phase multicomponent alloys without Al located in the Al-containing RHEAs region result from the addition of the FCC structural element Ni, as mentioned earlier. The solid solution phase formation rules for Ω can also be described as $\Omega \geq 5.40$ and $1.19 \leq \Omega \leq 8.81$ for Al-free and Al-containing RHEAs, respectively.

Effect of valence electron-related parameters on the phase stability of Co-free RHEAs

The parameters \overline{M}_d and VEC , which are both related to valence electrons, may be correlated in predicting HEA phases. Fig. 5 is generated by superimposing VEC and \overline{M}_d on three structures. The mixed phase in Al-free RHEAs exhibits a greater \overline{M}_d in FCC Ni than in the solid solution phase in Al-free RHEAs and the phases in Al-containing RHEAs. The difference between the solid solution phase in Al-free RHEAs and the phases in Al-containing RHEAs is difficult to describe. The \overline{M}_d in FCC Ni, BCC Fe and BCC Cr exhibit a convergent negative correlation with

Fig. 3. The distribution of δ superimposed $\overline{M_d}$ for FCC Ni (a), BCC Fe (b), BCC Cr (c) and VEC (d) in BCC-structured RHEAs.

Fig. 4. The distribution of δ superimposed on ΔS_{mix} , ΔH_{mix} and Ω in BCC-structured RHEAs.

VEC. In addition, Al-containing and Al-free RHEAs are distributed in parallel in the $\overline{M_d} - VEC$ plots. It is indicated that Al-containing RHEAs have lower $\overline{M_d}$ in BCC Fe and BCC Cr with comparable VEC values. The linear correlation of the phase distribution becomes increasingly divergent as FCC Ni changes to BCC Cr. Nevertheless, the mixed phase and BCC phase are difficult to distinguish in both the Al-free and Al-containing RHEAs from $\overline{M_d}$ (in the BCC Fe and BCC Cr) - VEC plots. This emphasizes the significance of selecting an appropriate $\overline{M_d}$ structure for predicting phases in Co-free RHEAs.

Discussion

Effect of ΔH_{mix} and δ on the stability of solid solution phases

According to the study by Guo et al., a two-dimensional $\Delta H_{mix} - \delta$ plot is essential for distinguishing between solid solution phases and amorphous phases in HEAs [115]. Singh et al. [104] noted the limitations of phase formation prediction based on the entropy of mixing; instead, the significance of the enthalpy of mixing and atomic size differences in the interpretation of disordered solid solution phase formation was emphasized. In the present study, the enthalpy of mixing and atomic size differences were also the most important parameters for

Fig. 5. Effect of $\overline{M}d$ for FCC Ni (a), BCC Fe (b) and BCC Cr (c) on VEC.

determining BCC phase formation in Co-free RHEAs. The enthalpy of mixing ΔH_{mix} is the miscibility of equimolar elements in binary liquid alloys [116]. Theoretically, the closer H is to 0, the more the atoms tend to be distributed in a disordered manner, favoring the formation of solid solution phases; conversely, the more negative H is, the stronger the bonding between the two elements is, favoring the formation of intermetallic phases. Since Zhang et al. [28] proposed the ΔH_{mix} range of -15 to $5 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ for solid solution formation rules in HEAs, it has been extended to -22 to $7 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ through the expansion of multicomponent alloy databases [117]. The criterion of $\Delta H_{mix} \geq -16.25 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ for solid solution phases in lightweight HEAs was defined by Feng et al. [118] and verified by an $\text{Al}_x\text{CrFeMnTi}_y$ alloy system. Furthermore, through the study of 16 RHEAs, Gao et al. [57] revealed that both the sign and absolute value of ΔH_{mix}^{BCC} are not necessarily in accordance with ΔH_{mix}^{liq} , which is calculated by the Miedema model. In general, the range of ΔH_{mix} for solid solution phase formation in HEAs is sensitive to the alloy system and component, and the value of ΔH_{mix} may change with the addition of FCC, BCC or HCP structural elements. Therefore, in this work, the solid solution phase formation rules in Co-free RHEAs considering the presence or absence of the nontransition element Al were considered. Two distinctly different ΔH_{mix} ranges for solid solution phase formation in Co-free RHEAs are proposed: $-6.24 - -2.72 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ and $-16.84 - -3.99 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ for Co-free RHEAs without and with the addition of Al, respectively. Notably, the Al-containing RHEAs $\text{Al}_5(\text{TiZrHfNb})_{95}$ and $\text{Al}_3(\text{TiZrHfNb})_{97}$ are listed in Table A1, have larger ΔH_{mix} values than the upper limit of BCC phase formation rules proposed in this work, which are -3.97 and $-1.46 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$, respectively. This is because the limits are defined by as-cast Co-free RHEAs, whereas these two alloys are in the recrystallized state. The as-homogenized/recrystallized Co-free RHEAs were added to show more information.

The Hume-Rothery rules state that small atomic size differences between constituent elements are one of the necessary conditions for the formation of solid solution phases in binary alloys [119]. As HEAs lack dominant elements, each constituent element can be regarded as a solute in relation to the others. The disorder in the distribution of solute atoms among solvent atoms is disrupted by large differences in atomic size. This causes lattice distortions and introduces strain energy, which reduces the stability of the solid solution phase. In addition, significant lattice distortions can impede atomic diffusion during solidification, resulting in the formation of intermetallic phases and potentially amorphous phases. The geometric factor δ is a widely used parameter for representing the atomic size differences among the constituent elements in HEAs. Generally, excess δ inhibits atomic diffusion and the formation of disordered solid solution phases, resulting in the generation of intermetallic compounds in HEAs [27,117,120]. Therefore, the mixed phases in Co-free RHEAs exhibit higher δ values than solid solution

phases as shown in Fig. 4b. It was initially proposed by summarizing multicomponent alloys from the literature that disordered solid solution phases are more stable in HEAs when $\delta \leq 6.5\%$ [28]. Subsequently, Zhang et al. [27] extended the upper limit of δ to 6.6% with the development of new multicomponent HEAs. Guo et al. [117] reported that solid solution phases can still form in HEAs even when δ is as high as 8.5% , which is based on the data from amorphous phase and solid solution phase alloy systems. The phase formation rules in HEAs should be promptly revised due to the rapid development of new multicomponent HEA systems. The values of δ are also affected by the alloy components and should be discussed separately for different alloy systems. Therefore, this work proposes δ limits of 6.28% and 7.63% for the formation of solid solution phases in Co-free RHEAs with and without the addition of Al, respectively. The next section will explore the reasons for the different δ limits. Although many other parameters, such as γ [121], Δ [122], $\Delta\chi$ [123] and ϕ [124], have been proposed to predict the phase of HEAs, the six parameters ΔS_{mix} , ΔH_{mix} , Ω , δ , $\overline{M}d$ and VEC are the most widely used parameters in current research.

Effect of the nontransition metal Al on the phase stability of RHEAs

Although pure aluminum has an FCC structure, Al is an important BCC phase tuning element for HEAs due to its BCC stabilizing nature and high solubility in Ti, Hf and Zr. According to previous reports, the phase components of CoCrCuFeNi alloys transition from a single FCC phase to a mixture of FCC and BCC phases and eventually transform into a BCC phase when the Al content reaches $2.8 \text{ at.}\%$ [125]. Guo et al. [29] proposed a correlation between VEC and the phase stability of HEAs in which $VEC \leq 6.87$ favors the formation of the BCC phase, and FCC is more stable when $VEC \geq 8.0$. The VEC values for the HEAs decreased from more than 8.0 to less than 6.87 with the addition of Al, resulting in a transition from the FCC phase to the BCC phase, as Al has the lowest VEC value compared to that of transition metals. The IM phase can be induced into Co-free RHEAs with the addition of Al due to the strong interaction between Al and constitutive elements of Co-free RHEAs, such as Ti and Zr [38,42,126]. It was found that C14Laves and IM phases are induced into the $\text{Al}_x\text{NbTiVZr}$ alloy with a higher Al content, and the volume fraction of the second phases is proportional to the Al content [38]. The large negative enthalpy of mixing leads to the aggregation of atoms in RHEAs, resulting in the formation of an ordered solid solution or IM phase [127]. This is exemplified by the large negative ΔH_{AB}^{mix} between Al and the other elements [128]. As illustrated in Fig. 5b, the addition of Al results in a decrease in the formation range for the ΔH_{mix} of BCC phases from $-6.24 - -2.72 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ to $-16.84 - -3.99 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$. The Al-containing RHEAs exhibits overall larger negative ΔH_{mix} values than did the Al-free RHEAs, which can be explained by

orbital hybridization. The electrons in the p -orbitals of Al easily transfer to the partially filled d -orbitals of the constitutive elements due to the high electron density of the p -orbitals and the high Fermi level of Al [102,129]. The hybrid pd -orbitals between Al and the constitutive elements cause the Al- X (X is a constitutive element) bonds to be shorter and stronger than the bonds among the constitutive elements. Therefore, Al-containing RHEAs have a more negative ΔH_{mix} than Al-free RHEAs. Although Al and some refractory elements, such as Nb, Ti and Ta, have similar atomic sizes, the δ limit for BCC phase stability in Al-containing RHEAs is 6.28 %, which is lower than the δ limit of 7.63 % in Al-free RHEAs due to the large negative enthalpy of mixing. According to the solid solution formation rules proposed by Zhang et al. [28], the ΔH_{mix} values of BCC phase formation rules in Al-free RHEAs are in the range of $-15 \leq \Delta H_{mix} \leq 5 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$, whereas the BCC phases in Al-containing RHEAs remain stable even when the ΔH_{mix} values are lower than this range. In contrast, the tolerance range of δ values for BCC phase stabilization in Al-free RHEAs is extended to 7.63 %, while the δ limit of 6.28 % for BCC phase formation in Al-containing RHEAs is in the range proposed by Zhang et al., which is $\delta \leq 6.6$ %. Therefore, the sensitivity of the BCC phase stability of Co-free RHEAs to ΔH_{mix} and δ is likely determined by the presence or absence of Al. As Al is added, Co-free RHEAs become more sensitive to the values of δ than to the values of ΔH_{mix} . Accordingly, it is necessary to consider alloying systems with or without Al separately and select appropriate parameters when predicting the phase of Co-free RHEAs.

Conclusions

In the present study, the semiempirical parameters \overline{M}_d , VEC , ΔS_{mix} , ΔH_{mix} , Ω and δ of multicomponent Co-free RHEAs were carefully calculated to determine the solid solution phase formation rules, taking into account the effect of Al. The following conclusions were reached:

- (1) The parameters ΔH_{mix} and δ are more effective at distinguishing the BCC phase and BCC + IM mixed phase stabilities in Co-free RHEAs than are other semiempirical parameters.
- (2) A clear difference in the $\Delta H_{mix} - \delta$ plot was observed for the Co-free RHEAs depending on the presence or absence of Al. The Al-containing RHEAs exhibited overall larger negative ΔH_{mix} values than did the Al-free RHEAs. The mixed phases in Co-free RHEAs exhibit higher δ values than solid solution phases.
- (3) The solid solution phases in Co-free RHEAs without the addition of Al simultaneously occur when $-6.24 \leq \Delta H_{mix} \leq 2.72 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ and $\delta \leq 7.63$ %. For Co-free RHEAs with the addition of Al, solid

solution phases are prone to form when $-16.84 \leq \Delta H_{mix} \leq -3.99 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ and $\delta \leq 6.28$ %.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Yulin Li: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Łukasz Kurpaska:** Writing – review & editing. **Eryang Lu:** Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis. **Zonghan Xie:** Writing – review & editing. **Hyoungh Seop Kim:** Writing – review & editing. **Wenyi Huo:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix

Table A1

Compositions of Co-free RHEAs and the parameters ΔS_{mix} , ΔH_{mix} , Ω , δ , \overline{M}_d , VEC , phases and state. Note: the intermetallic phases are denoted as IM.

Materials	ΔS_{mix} (J·K ⁻¹ ·mol ⁻¹)	ΔH_{mix} (kJ·mol ⁻¹)	Ω	δ	\overline{M}_d			VEC	Phase	State	Ref.
					M in FCC Ni	M in BCC Fe	M in BCC Cr				
Al _{0.25} CrNbTiVZr	14.34	-8.49	3.67	8.46	1.998	2.064	2.371	4.71	BCC + IM	as- homogenized	[31]
Al _{0.25} HfNbTiZr	12.71	-5.04	5.67	4.92	2.548	2.664	3.216	4.18	BCC	as-cast	[32]
Al _{0.25} NbTaTiV	12.71	-4.82	6.45	3.82	2.031	2.162	2.681	4.65	BCC	as-cast	[33]
Al _{0.3} HfNbTaTiZr	14.43	-3.99	8.81	4.97	2.480	2.615	3.269	4.32	BCC	as-cast	[102]
Al _{0.3} NbTa _{0.8} Ti _{1.4} V _{0.2} Zr _{1.3}	13.46	-4.86	6.41	5.30	2.356	2.490	2.928	4.34	BCC	as-cast	[34]
Al _{0.3} NbTaTi _{1.4} Zr _{1.3}	12.63	-4.41	6.76	4.83	2.384	2.525	2.992	4.34	BCC	as-cast	[34]
Al _{0.4} Hf _{0.6} NbTaTiZr	14.50	-6.33	5.49	4.93	2.426	2.540	3.124	4.32	BCC	as-cast	[103]
Al _{0.5} Cr _{0.5} MoNbTiZr	14.53	-11.84	2.77	7.03	2.081	2.123	2.405	4.70	BCC + IM	as- homogenized	[35]
Al _{0.5} Cr _{1.5} NbTiZr	12.95	-13.84	1.97	8.87	1.999	2.002	2.272	4.70	BCC + IM	as- homogenized	[35]

(continued on next page)

Table A1 (continued)

Materials	ΔS_{mix} (J·K ⁻¹ ·mol ⁻¹)	ΔH_{mix} (kJ·mol ⁻¹)	Ω	δ	\overline{M}			VEC	Phase	State	Ref.
					M in FCC Ni	M in BCC Fe	M in BCC Cr				
Al _{0.5} CrMo _{0.5} NbTiZr	14.53	-12.84	2.47	8.03	2.040	2.063	2.339	4.70	BCC + IM	as- homogenized	[35]
Al _{0.5} CrNb _{0.5} TiV	12.97	-11.63	2.27	6.28	1.741	1.713	2.004	4.75	BCC	as-cast	[36]
Al _{0.5} CrNbTiVZr	14.70	-11.64	2.68	8.26	1.994	2.017	2.310	4.64	BCC + IM	as- homogenized	[31]
Al _{0.5} HfNbTaTiZr	14.70	-7.67	4.56	4.95	2.459	2.558	3.187	4.27	BCC	as-cast	[102]
Al _{0.5} HfNbTiZr	13.15	-10.96	2.61	4.95	2.512	2.574	3.095	4.11	BCC	as-cast	[32]
Al _{0.5} Mo _{1.5} NbTiZr	12.95	-10.84	2.78	5.80	2.121	2.184	2.472	4.70	BCC + IM	as- homogenized	[35]
Al _{0.5} Nb _{0.5} Ti ₂ VZr	12.23	-11.04	2.22	6.28	2.208	2.273	2.589	4.20	BCC	as-cast	[37]
Al _{0.5} NbTa _{0.8} Ti _{1.5} V _{0.2} Zr	13.78	-8.62	3.62	4.93	2.301	2.396	2.825	4.30	BCC	as-cast	[34]
Al _{0.5} NbTaTiV	13.15	-8.40	3.70	3.73	2.023	2.099	2.589	4.56	BCC	as-cast	[33]
Al _{0.5} NbTiVZr	13.15	-10.86	2.55	6.66	2.183	2.230	2.535	4.33	BCC + IM	as-cast	[38]
Al _{0.75} HfNbTaTiZr	14.85	-11.55	2.98	4.92	2.435	2.492	3.094	4.22	BCC	as-cast	[102]
Al _{0.75} HfNbTiZr	13.33	-15.65	1.80	4.96	2.479	2.493	2.986	4.05	BCC	as-cast	[32]
Al _{1.5} Cr _{0.5} NbTiZr	12.95	-24.40	0.99	6.49	2.151	1.997	2.219	4.10	BCC + IM	as- homogenized	[35]
Al _{1.5} Mo _{0.5} NbTiZr	12.95	-23.00	1.09	5.03	2.204	2.058	2.285	4.10	BCC + IM	as- homogenized	[35]
Al _{1.5} NbTiVZr	13.25	-21.55	1.16	6.06	2.132	2.012	2.262	4.09	BCC + IM	as-cast	[38]
Al ₁₂ (TiZrHfNb) ₈₈	13.19	-11.90	2.40	4.95	2.505	2.558	3.074	4.10	BCC	as- recrystallized	[39]
Al ₂₀ Mo ₁₀ Nb ₂₀ Ti ₃₀ V ₂₀	12.95	-14.16	1.87	3.86	1.948	1.911	2.197	4.40	BCC	as-cast	[41]
Al ₃ (TiZrHfNb) ₉₇	12.30	-1.46	19.29	4.89	2.567	2.714	3.283	4.21	BCC	as- recrystallized	[39]
Al ₅ (TiZrHfNb) ₉₅	12.60	-3.97	7.18	4.93	2.554	2.680	3.236	4.19	BCC	as- recrystallized	[39]
Al ₇ (TiZrHfNb) ₉₃	12.83	-6.37	4.50	4.93	2.540	2.645	3.190	4.16	BCC	as- recrystallized	[39]
AlCr _{0.5} Mo _{0.5} NbTiZr	14.53	-18.32	1.63	6.78	2.116	2.060	2.312	4.40	BCC + IM	as- homogenized	[35]
AlCr _{0.5} NbTa _{0.5} Ti _{3.5}	10.84	-13.85	1.59	3.85	2.100	2.136	2.491	4.23	BCC	as-cast	[40]
AlCr _{0.5} NbTaTi ₃	11.79	-13.30	1.89	3.81	2.096	2.135	2.548	4.31	BCC	as-cast	[40]
AlCr _{0.5} NbTi ₄	8.91	-14.44	1.19	3.87	2.103	2.136	2.435	4.15	BCC	as-cast	[40]
AlCrMoNbTi	13.38	-13.60	2.11	5.49	1.796	1.718	1.967	4.80	BCC	as-cast	[42]
AlCrMoTaTi	13.38	-13.76	2.19	5.50	1.817	1.748	2.156	4.80	BCC + IM	as- homogenized	[43]
AlCrMoTiW	13.38	-10.08	3.09	5.32	1.704	1.618	1.988	5.00	BCC	as-cast	[44]
AlCrNbTiVZr	14.90	-16.33	1.84	7.91	1.986	1.935	2.204	4.50	BCC + IM	as- homogenized	[31]
AlCrNbTiZr	13.38	-19.52	1.36	7.84	2.075	2.000	2.245	4.40	BCC + IM	as- homogenized	[35]
AlCrNi _{1.5} NbTi _{3.52} V	13.64	-23.82	1.11	6.69	1.748	1.754	1.931	5.33	BCC + IM	as-cast	[45]
AlCuHfNiTiZr	14.90	-34.11	0.77	9.43	1.911	1.844	1.941	6.00	IM	as-cast	[46]
AlFeNiTiVZr	14.90	-31.33	0.85	9.34	1.706	1.617	1.695	5.67	BMG	as-cast	[47]
AlHfNbTaTiZr	14.90	-15.11	2.23	4.89	2.413	2.431	3.008	4.17	BCC	as-cast	[102]
AlHfNbTiZr	13.38	-19.36	1.42	4.96	2.450	2.420	2.889	4.00	BCC + IM	as-cast	[32]
AlMo _{0.5} NbTa _{0.5} TiZr	14.53	-16.84	1.87	5.03	2.224	2.203	2.542	4.30	BCC	as-cast	[103]
AlMoNbTiZr	13.38	-17.12	1.66	5.45	2.156	2.121	2.379	4.40	BCC + IM	as- homogenized	[35]
AlNb _{1.5} Ta _{0.5} Ti _{1.5} Zr _{0.5}	12.51	-15.12	1.77	3.46	2.213	2.212	2.563	4.20	BCC	as-cast	[34]
AlNb _{1.5} Ta _{0.5} Ti ₃ Zr ₄	11.58	-10.48	2.32	5.16	2.478	2.557	2.888	4.10	BCC + IM	as- homogenized	[48]
AlNbNiTaTiW	14.90	-22.89	1.56	5.17	1.814	1.808	2.192	5.50	BCC + IM	as-cast	[49]
AlNbTaTiV	13.38	-13.44	2.21	3.55	2.011	1.992	2.434	4.40	BCC	as-cast	[33]
AlNbTaTiZr	13.38	-16.16	1.83	4.54	2.291	2.285	2.706	4.20	BCC + IM	as-cast	[50]
AlNbTiV	11.53	-16.25	1.38	3.94	1.958	1.869	2.141	4.25	BCC	as-cast	[51]
AlNbTiVZr	13.38	-17.44	1.52	6.33	2.155	2.110	2.385	4.20	BCC + IM	as-cast	[38]
AlNbTiVZr _{0.5}	13.15	-17.19	1.51	5.60	2.067	2.003	2.276	4.22	BCC + IM	as- homogenized	[52]
AlNbTiZr	11.53	-21.50	1.04	4.81	2.308	2.235	2.481	4.00	BCC + IM	as-cast	[53]
Cr _{0.1} Hf _{0.5} Mo _{0.5} NbTiZr	13.60	-0.96	33.53	6.21	2.373	2.542	2.991	4.54	BCC + IM	as- homogenized	[54]
Cr _{0.3} Hf _{0.2} NbTaZr	12.04	0.02	1,636.74	7.05	2.352	2.527	3.120	4.74	BCC + IM	as-cast	[55]

(continued on next page)

Table A1 (continued)

Materials	ΔS_{mix} (J·K ⁻¹ ·mol ⁻¹)	ΔH_{mix} (kJ·mol ⁻¹)	Ω	δ	\bar{M}_d			VEC	Phase	State	Ref.
					M in FCC Ni	M in BCC Fe	M in BCC Cr				
Cr _{0.5} Hf _{0.2} NbTaZr	12.38	-1.61	20.32	7.73	2.286	2.448	3.022	4.81	BCC + IM	as-cast	[55]
Cr _{0.5} Mo _{1.5} NbTiZr	12.95	-4.96	6.40	7.25	2.046	2.186	2.499	5.00	BCC + IM	as- homogenized	[35]
Cr _{0.5} MoNbTaVW	14.70	-4.83	8.81	4.10	1.756	1.902	2.482	5.45	BCC	as-cast	[56]
Cr _{0.75} Hf _{0.2} NbTaZr	12.55	-3.19	10.26	8.35	2.214	2.360	2.913	4.89	BCC + IM	as-cast	[55]
Cr _{1.5} Mo _{0.5} NbTiZr	12.95	-6.56	4.55	8.98	1.964	2.065	2.365	5.00	BCC + IM	as- homogenized	[35]
Cr ₂ MoNbTaVW	14.53	-4.82	8.26	5.22	1.625	1.721	2.229	5.57	BCC	as-cast	[56]
CrHf _{0.2} NbTaZr	12.57	-4.40	7.38	8.78	2.150	2.282	2.817	4.95	BCC + IM	as-cast	[55]
CrHfMoNbTaTiVWZr	18.27	-4.84	9.89	7.63	2.052	2.191	2.783	5.00	BCC	as-cast	[57]
CrMoNbTaV	13.38	-4.64	7.67	5.09	1.715	1.831	2.307	5.40	BCC	as-cast	[58]
CrMoNbTaVW	14.90	-4.89	8.63	4.65	1.705	1.832	2.384	5.50	BCC	as-cast	[56]
CrMoNbTaW	13.38	-6.24	6.35	4.82	1.738	1.876	2.461	5.60	BCC	as-cast	[59]
CrMoNbTiZr	13.38	-5.76	5.53	8.19	2.005	2.126	2.432	5.00	BCC + IM	as- homogenized	[35]
CrMoTaTi	11.53	-5.50	5.40	5.92	1.797	1.926	2.436	5.25	BCC	as-cast	[60]
CrMoVW	11.53	-0.50	63.13	3.59	1.473	1.542	2.009	5.75	BCC	as-cast	[61]
CrNbTa _{0.25} TiZr	12.71	-4.60	6.39	8.51	2.125	2.256	2.610	4.76	BCC + IM	as-cast	[62]
CrNbTaTi	11.53	-4.50	6.51	6.02	1.939	2.094	2.610	5.00	BCC	as-cast	[60]
CrNbTaTiZr	13.38	-3.68	8.94	7.85	2.140	2.290	2.759	4.80	BCC + IM	as-cast	[50]
CrNbTiVZr	13.38	-4.64	6.45	8.67	2.003	2.115	2.438	4.80	BCC + IM	as- homogenized	[63]
CrNbTiZr	11.53	-5.00	5.19	8.77	2.119	2.241	2.548	4.75	BCC + IM	as- homogenized	[63]
CrTaTiV	11.53	-4.50	6.14	6.28	1.795	1.913	2.444	5.00	BCC + IM	as-cast	[65]
CuFeHfTiZr	13.38	-15.84	1.65	10.41	1.942	2.038	2.219	6.20	IM	as-cast	[66]
CuFeNiTiVZr	14.90	-18.78	1.47	9.74	1.491	1.551	1.465	7.00	BMG	as-cast	[47]
CuHfNiTiZr	13.38	-27.36	0.94	10.32	1.913	2.006	2.123	6.60	BMG	as-cast	[66]
CuNbNiTiZr	13.38	-21.28	1.25	9.25	1.733	1.841	1.752	6.80	BMG	as-cast	[67]
FeMoNiTiVZr	14.90	-19.78	1.59	9.29	1.647	1.722	1.850	6.17	BMG	as-cast	[47]
Hf _{0.25} NbTaW _{0.5}	10.51	-3.44	9.46	3.62	2.154	2.374	3.193	5.09	BCC	as-cast	[68]
Hf _{0.5} Nb _{0.5} Ta _{0.5} Ti _{1.5} Zr	12.42	1.88	15.42	4.79	2.508	2.702	3.264	4.25	BCC	as-cast	[69]
Hf _{0.5} NbTi ₂ VZr	12.60	0.00	N/A	6.42	2.301	2.471	2.912	4.36	BCC + IM	as- homogenized	[31]
Hf _{18.49} Mo _{8.97} Nb _{12.7} Ta _{0.19} Ti _{32.07} Zr _{27.58}	12.66	-0.32	90.14	5.45	2.511	2.683	3.204	4.31	BCC	as-cast	[70]
Hf _{20.39} Mo _{5.57} Nb _{12.05} Ta _{0.80} Ti _{32.61} Zr _{28.58}	12.49	0.29	97.28	5.20	2.557	2.731	3.276	4.24	BCC	as-cast	[70]
Hf ₂ Nb ₂ Ti ₃ V ₁₅ W ₃	11.88	-0.05	529.98	5.63	2.282	2.461	3.069	4.43	BCC	as-cast	[71]
Hf _{28.33} Mo _{1.55} Nb _{6.74} Ta _{6.74} Ti _{28.33} Zr _{28.33}	12.47	1.01	28.68	4.74	2.649	2.823	3.497	4.17	BCC	as-cast	[70]
Hf ₅ Nb ₅₅ Ta ₂₅ Ti ₁₅	9.23	1.40	18.13	2.30	2.212	2.438	3.022	4.80	BCC	as-cast	[72]
HfMo _{0.25} NbTaTiZr	14.34	1.56	23.35	5.27	2.469	2.660	3.334	4.48	BCC	as-cast	[73]
HfMo _{0.5} NbTaTiZr	14.70	0.60	63.15	5.47	2.427	2.615	3.272	4.55	BCC	as-cast	[73]
HfMo _{0.75} NbTaTiZr	14.85	-0.21	180.43	5.65	2.389	2.574	3.216	4.61	BCC	as-cast	[73]
HfMoNbTaTi	13.38	-1.44	24.87	4.86	2.236	2.428	3.125	4.80	BCC + IM	as-cast	[74]
HfMoNbTaTiVWZr	17.29	-3.44	12.75	6.60	2.166	2.333	2.969	4.88	BCC	as-cast	[57]
HfMoNbTaTiVZr	16.18	-1.47	27.83	6.68	2.238	2.403	2.997	4.71	BCC	as-cast	[57]
HfMoNbTaTiWZr	16.18	-3.59	12.36	6.02	2.254	2.436	3.107	4.86	BCC	as-cast	[75]
HfMoNbTaTiZr	14.90	-0.89	43.32	5.78	2.354	2.536	3.164	4.67	BCC	as-cast	[76]
HfMoNbTaW	13.38	-4.64	8.73	5.43	2.113	2.296	3.104	5.20	BCC	as-cast	[59]
HfMoNbTiZr	13.38	-1.60	20.44	6.10	2.380	2.546	3.075	4.60	BCC	as-cast	[77]
HfMoTaTiVZr	14.90	-2.33	15.90	7.15	2.259	2.415	3.053	4.67	BCC	as-cast	[57]
HfMoTaTiZr	13.38	-1.92	17.79	6.08	2.402	2.576	3.264	4.60	BCC	as-cast	[76]
HfNb _{0.18} Ta _{0.18} Ti _{1.27} Zr	11.44	0.97	26.50	4.48	2.653	2.830	3.485	4.10	BCC + IM	as-cast	[78]
HfNbTaTiV	13.38	0.64	52.98	5.79	2.235	2.417	3.131	4.60	BCC	as-cast	[79]
HfNbTaTiVZr	14.90	0.44	82.67	6.59	2.353	2.527	3.169	4.50	BCC	as-cast	[80]
HfNbTaTiWZr	14.90	-2.11	19.18	5.71	2.372	2.565	3.297	4.67	BCC	as-cast	[75]
HfNbTaTiZr	13.38	2.72	12.41	4.98	2.515	2.710	3.403	4.40	BCC	as-cast	[81]
HfNbTiVZr	13.38	0.16	192.48	7.05	2.379	2.535	3.081	4.40	BCC	as-cast	[82]
HfNbTiZr	11.53	2.50	10.75	4.86	2.588	2.766	3.352	4.25	BCC	as- homogenized	[83]
HfTa _{0.2} Ti ₂ V _{0.5} Zr	11.60	-0.63	39.97	5.95	2.494	2.666	3.263	4.15	BCC	as-cast	[84]
Mo _{0.5} NbHf _{0.5} ZrTi	12.97	-0.25	123.44	5.72	2.404	2.579	3.034	4.50	BCC	as-cast	[58]
Mo ₁₀ (NbTaTiZr) ₉₀	13.08	0.14	248.36	5.22	2.305	2.505	3.008	4.65	BCC	as-cast	[85]
Mo ₁₅ (NbTaTiZr) ₈₅	13.31	-0.87	39.46	5.35	2.263	2.458	2.951	4.73	BCC	as-cast	[85]
Mo ₅ (NbTaTiZr) ₉₅	12.60	1.26	25.48	5.04	2.347	2.551	3.066	4.58	BCC	as-cast	[85]
MoNb _{1.3} TaTiW _{0.4}	12.91	-4.09	8.86	2.57	2.013	2.216	2.768	5.09	BCC	as-cast	[86]

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Table A1 (continued)

Materials	ΔS_{mix} (J·K ⁻¹ ·mol ⁻¹)	ΔH_{mix} (kJ·mol ⁻¹)	Ω	δ	\bar{M}_d			VEC	Phase	State	Ref.
					M in FCC Ni	M in BCC Fe	M in BCC Cr				
MoNbTa _{0.3} V	10.84	-3.23	8.96	3.45	1.781	1.925	2.336	5.30	BCC	as-cast	[87]
MoNbTa _{0.5} V	11.24	-3.27	9.32	3.48	1.806	1.957	2.409	5.29	BCC	as-cast	[87]
MoNbTa _{0.7} V	11.44	-3.27	9.57	3.48	1.829	1.986	2.473	5.27	BCC	as-cast	[87]
MoNbTaTi _{0.25} W	12.71	-6.15	6.38	2.49	1.909	2.105	2.758	5.41	BCC	as-cast	[88]
MoNbTaTi _{0.5} W	13.15	-5.83	6.82	2.61	1.929	2.126	2.764	5.33	BCC	as-cast	[88]
MoNbTaTi _{0.5} Zr	13.15	-2.07	16.95	5.75	2.216	2.401	2.895	4.89	BCC	as-cast	[89]
MoNbTaTi _{0.75} W	13.33	-5.54	7.14	2.66	1.947	2.146	2.770	5.26	BCC	as-cast	[88]
MoNbTaTi _{1.5} Zr	13.25	-1.52	22.15	5.20	2.226	2.419	2.891	4.73	BCC	as-cast	[89]
MoNbTaTi ₂ Zr	12.98	-1.33	24.24	4.98	2.230	2.425	2.889	4.67	BCC	as-cast	[89]
MoNbTaTiV	13.38	-2.56	13.65	3.78	1.941	2.118	2.621	5.00	BCC	as-cast	[90]
MoNbTaTiVW	14.90	-4.22	9.85	3.58	1.893	2.071	2.645	5.17	BCC	as-cast	[91]
MoNbTaTiVZr	14.90	-2.11	17.86	6.24	2.108	2.278	2.744	4.83	BCC	as-cast	[92]
MoNbTaTiW	13.38	-5.28	7.39	2.77	1.963	2.163	2.775	5.20	BCC	as-cast	[88]
MoNbTaTiZr	13.38	-1.76	19.77	5.45	2.221	2.411	2.893	4.80	BCC	as-cast	[85]
MoNbTaV	11.53	-3.25	9.86	3.46	1.859	2.024	2.558	5.25	BCC	as-cast	[93]
MoNbTaV _{0.25}	10.69	-4.36	7.16	2.77	1.931	2.119	2.688	5.31	BCC	as-cast	[94]
MoNbTaV _{0.5}	11.24	-3.92	8.22	3.11	1.904	2.083	2.638	5.29	BCC	as-cast	[94]
MoNbTaV _{0.75}	11.47	-3.56	9.09	3.32	1.880	2.051	2.596	5.27	BCC	as-cast	[94]
MoNbTaVW	13.38	-4.64	8.54	3.15	1.818	1.986	2.600	5.40	BCC	as-cast	[95]
MoNbTaW	11.53	-6.50	5.60	2.32	1.887	2.080	2.751	5.50	BCC	as-cast	[95]
MoNbTaWZr	13.38	-5.44	7.26	6.06	2.098	2.279	2.872	5.20	BCC	as-cast	[96]
MoNbTaWZr _{0.1}	12.20	-6.38	5.99	3.21	1.912	2.104	2.766	5.46	BCC	as-cast	[96]
MoNbTaWZr _{0.3}	12.83	-6.14	6.44	4.32	1.960	2.149	2.793	5.40	BCC	as-cast	[96]
MoNbTaWZr _{0.5}	13.15	-5.93	6.75	5.03	2.004	2.190	2.818	5.33	BCC	as-cast	[96]
MoNbTiV	11.53	-2.75	10.24	4.06	1.870	2.026	2.375	5.00	BCC	as-cast	[97]
MoNbTiV _{0.25} Zr	12.71	-2.60	11.79	6.31	2.181	2.346	2.673	4.76	BCC	as-cast	[98]
MoNbTiV _{0.5} Zr	13.15	-2.67	11.84	6.55	2.145	2.305	2.635	4.78	BCC	as-cast	[98]
MoNbTiV _{0.75} Zr	14.85	-2.70	8.24	6.47	2.114	2.269	2.602	5.00	BCC	as-cast	[98]
MoNbTiV _{1.5} Zr	13.25	-2.71	11.55	6.99	2.036	2.179	2.519	4.82	BCC	as-cast	[98]
MoNbTiV ₂ Zr	12.98	-2.67	11.42	7.06	1.995	2.132	2.476	4.83	BCC	as-cast	[98]
MoNbTiV ₃ Zr	12.26	-2.53	11.26	7.04	1.930	2.057	2.408	4.86	BCC	as-cast	[98]
MoNbTiVZr	14.90	-2.72	8.50	6.53	2.085	2.236	2.571	5.00	BCC	as-cast	[98]
MoNbTiZr	11.53	-2.50	11.20	5.98	2.221	2.392	2.715	4.75	BCC	as-cast	[98]
MoNbV	9.13	-3.11	7.66	3.39	1.737	1.869	2.209	5.33	BCC	as-cast	[87]
MoTaVWZr	13.38	-4.80	7.91	7.09	1.983	2.134	2.740	5.20	BCC + IM	as-cast	[99]
Nb _{0.25} Ta _{0.1} Ti _{0.3} V _{0.25} Zr _{0.1}	12.59	-0.11	269.91	5.66	2.113	2.291	2.722	4.60	BCC	as-cast	[100]
Nb _{0.5} TiV _{0.5} Zr	11.05	-0.11	216.75	6.77	2.348	2.515	2.853	4.33	BCC	as-homogenized	[101]
NbTaTiV	11.53	-0.25	117.15	3.92	2.039	2.232	2.784	4.75	BCC	as-cast	[33]
NbTaTiVZr	13.38	0.32	102.80	6.34	2.220	2.400	2.899	4.60	BCC	as-cast	[57]
NbTaTiW	11.53	-4.50	7.48	2.41	2.067	2.289	2.976	5.00	BCC	as-cast	[60]
NbTaTiZr	11.53	2.50	11.65	4.83	2.389	2.598	3.124	4.50	BCC	as-cast	[85]
NbTi ₂ VZr	11.08	-0.16	151.50	6.28	2.229	2.403	2.752	4.40	BCC	as-cast	[37]
NbTiV ₂ Zr	11.08	-1.28	19.36	7.46	2.084	2.225	2.577	4.60	BCC	as-homogenized	[63]
NbTiVZr	11.53	-0.25	103.75	7.03	2.219	2.379	2.722	4.50	BCC	as-cast	[64]

References

- [1] Zhang Z, Armstrong DE, Grant PS. The effects of irradiation on CrMnFeCoNi high-entropy alloy and its derivatives. *Prog Mater Sci* 2022;123:100807. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pmatsci.2021.100807>.
- [2] Cantor B, Chang I, Knight P, Vincent A. Microstructural development in equiatomic multicomponent alloys. *Mater Sci Eng A* 2004;375:213–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.msea.2003.10.257>.
- [3] Yeh JW, Chen SK, Lin SJ, Gan JY, Chin TS, Shun TT, et al. Nanostructured high-entropy alloys with multiple principal elements: novel alloy design concepts and outcomes. *Adv Eng Mater* 2004;6(5):299–303. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adem.200300567>.
- [4] Aygün B. High alloyed new stainless steel shielding material for gamma and fast neutron radiation. *Nucl Eng Technol* 2020;52(3):647–53. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.net.2019.08.017>.
- [5] Waheed F, Rwashdi QAAD, Gunoglu K, Akkurt İ. Experimental testing of the radiation shielding properties for steel. *Int J Comput Sci Eng* 2022;8(3):74–6. <https://doi.org/10.22399/ijcesen.1067028>.
- [6] Han W, Demkowicz M, Fu E, Wang Y, Misra A. Effect of grain boundary character on sink efficiency. *Acta Mater* 2012;60(18):6341–51. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actamat.2012.08.009>.
- [7] Ding MS, Du JP, Wan L, Ogata S, Tian L, Ma E, et al. Radiation-induced helium nanobubbles enhance ductility in submicron-sized single-crystalline copper. *Nano Lett* 2016;16(7):4118–24. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.nanolett.6b00864>.
- [8] Lloyd M, London A, Haley J, Gilbert M, Bequart C, Domain C, et al. Interaction of transmutation products with precipitates, dislocations and grain boundaries in neutron irradiated W. *Materialia* 2022;22:101370. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mta.2022.101370>.
- [9] Ardell AJ, Bellon P. Radiation-induced solute segregation in metallic alloys. *Curr Opin Solid State Mater Sci* 2016;20(3):115–39. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cossms.2015.11.001>.
- [10] Huo W, Fang F, Liu X, Tan S, Xie Z, Jiang J. Fatigue resistance of nanotwinned high-entropy alloy films. *Mater Sci Eng A* 2019;739:26–30. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.msea.2018.09.112>.
- [11] Huo W, Fang F, Liu X, Tan S, Xie Z, Jiang J. Remarkable strain-rate sensitivity of nanotwinned CoCrFeNi alloys. *Appl Phys Lett* 2019;114:101904. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.5088921>.
- [12] Zhao Y, Yang T, Zhu J, Chen D, Yang Y, Hu A, et al. Development of high-strength Co-free high-entropy alloys hardened by nanosized precipitates. *Scr Mater* 2018;148:51–5. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scriptamat.2018.01.028>.
- [13] Zhu W, Huo W, Wang S, Kurpaska L, Fang F, Papanikolaou S, et al. Machine learning based hardness prediction of high-entropy alloys for laser additive manufacturing. *JOM* 2023;75:5537–48. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11837-023-06174-x>.
- [14] Barr CM, Nathaniel II JE, Unocic KA, Liu J, Zhang Y, Wang Y, et al. Exploring radiation induced segregation mechanisms at grain boundaries in equiatomic CoCrFeNiMn high entropy alloy under heavy ion irradiation. *Scr Mater* 2018;156:80–4. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scriptamat.2018.06.041>.

- [15] Kumar NK, Li C, Leonard K, Bei H, Zinkle S. Microstructural stability and mechanical behavior of FeNiMnCr high entropy alloy under ion irradiation. *Acta Mater* 2016;113:230–44. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actamat.2016.05.007>.
- [16] Huo W, Wang S, Fang F, Tan S, Kurpaska L, Xie Z, et al. Microstructure and corrosion resistance of highly <111> oriented electrodeposited CoNiFe medium-entropy alloy films. *J Mater Res Technol* 2022;20:1677–84. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmrt.2022.07.175>.
- [17] Wang K, Jin X, Zhang Y, Liaw PK, Qiao J. Dynamic tensile mechanisms and constitutive relationship in CrFeNi medium entropy alloys at room and cryogenic temperatures. *Phys Rev Mater* 2021;5(11):113608. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevMaterials.5.113608>.
- [18] Bian BB, Guo N, Yang HJ, Guo RP, Yang L, Wu YC, et al. A novel cobalt-free FeMnCrNi medium-entropy alloy with exceptional yield strength and ductility at cryogenic temperature. *J Alloys Compd* 2020;827:153981. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2020.153981>.
- [19] He MR, Wang S, Shi S, Jin K, Bei H, Yasuda K, et al. Mechanisms of radiation-induced segregation in CrFeCoNi-based single-phase concentrated solid solution alloys. *Acta Mater* 2017;126:182–93. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actamat.2016.12.046>.
- [20] Xia SQ, Yang X, Yang TF, Liu S, Zhang Y. Irradiation resistance in Al_xCoCrFeNi high entropy alloys. *JOM* 2015;67(10):2340–4. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11837-015-1568-4>.
- [21] Manescau TJ, Braun J, Dezellus O. Computational development, synthesis and mechanical properties of face centered cubic Co-free high entropy alloys. *Mater Today Commun* 2022;30:103202. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mtcomm.2022.103202>.
- [22] Ocken H. Reducing the cobalt inventory in light water reactors. *Nucl Technol* 1985;68(1):18–28. <https://doi.org/10.13182/NT85-A33563>.
- [23] Cao PP, Huang HL, Jiang SH, Liu XJ, Wang H, Wu Y, et al. Microstructural stability and aging behavior of refractory high entropy alloys at intermediate temperatures. *J Mater Sci Technol* 2022;122:243–54. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmst.2021.12.057>.
- [24] Zhou JL, Cheng YH, Chen YX, Liang XB. Composition design and preparation process of refractory high-entropy alloys: a review. *Int J Refract Met Hard Mater* 2022;105:105836. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijrmhm.2022.105836>.
- [25] Chen J, Zhou X, Wang W, Liu B, Lv Y, Yang W, et al. A review on fundamental of high entropy alloys with promising high-temperature properties. *J Alloys Compd* 2018;760:15–30. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2018.05.067>.
- [26] Wang L, Liu X, Li C, Yang M, Wang B, Ming K, et al. Remarkable ductility in metastable refractory high entropy alloys via BCC-FCC/ α' martensitic transformations. *J Appl Phys* 2021;119(15):151902. <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0064897>.
- [27] Yang X, Zhang Y. Prediction of high-entropy stabilized solid-solution in multi-component alloys. *Mater Chem Phys* 2012;132(2):233–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matchemphys.2011.11.021>.
- [28] Zhang Y, Zhou YJ, Lin JP, Chen GL, Liaw PK. Solid-solution phase formation rules for multi-component alloys. *Adv Eng Mater* 2008;10(6):534–8. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adem.200700240>.
- [29] Guo S, Ng C, Lu J, Liu CT. Effect of valence electron concentration on stability of fcc or bcc phase in high entropy alloys. *J Appl Phys* 2011;109(10):103505. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.3587228>.
- [30] Lu Y, Dong Y, Jiang L, Wang T, Li T, Zhang Y. A criterion for topological close-packed phase formation in high entropy alloys. *Entropy* 2015;2355–66. <https://doi.org/10.3390/e17042355>.
- [31] Yurchenko NY, Stepanov ND, Shaysultanov DG, Tikhonovsky MA, Salishchev GA. Effect of Al content on structure and mechanical properties of the Al_xCrNbTiVZr ($x=0; 0.25; 0.5; 1$) high-entropy alloys. *Mater Charact* 2016;121:125–134. doi: 10.1016/j.matchar.2016.09.039.
- [32] Bhardwaj V, Zhou Q, Zhang F, Han W, Du Y, Hua K, et al. Effect of Al addition on the microstructure, mechanical and wear properties of TiZrNbHf refractory high entropy alloys. *Tribol Int* 2021;160:107031. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.triboint.2021.107031>.
- [33] Yang X, Zhang Y, Liaw PK. Microstructure and compressive properties of NbTiVTaAl_x High entropy alloys. *Procedia Eng* 2012;36:292–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proeng.2012.03.043>.
- [34] Senkov ON, Woodward C, Miracle DB. Microstructure and properties of aluminum-containing refractory high-entropy alloys. *JOM* 2014;66(10):2030–42. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11837-014-1066-0>.
- [35] Auyeskan U, Lee HM, Ryu HJ, Waseem OA. A combinatorial approach for the synthesis and analysis of Al_xCr_yMo_zNbTiZr high-entropy alloys: Oxidation behavior. *J Mater Res* 2018;33(19):3226–34. <https://doi.org/10.1557/jmr.2018.241>.
- [36] Li M, Chen Q, Cui X, Peng X, Huang G. Evaluation of corrosion resistance of the single-phase light refractory high entropy alloy TiCrVNb_{0.5}Al_{0.5} in chloride environment. *J Alloys Compd* 2021;857:158278. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2020.158278>.
- [37] An Z, Mao S, Yang T, Liu Y, Chen Y, Yang X, et al. Han X. Simultaneously enhanced oxidation resistance and mechanical properties in a novel lightweight Ti₂VZrNb_{0.5}Al_{0.5} high-entropy alloy. *Sci China Mater* 2022;65(10):2842–9. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40843-022-2045-4>.
- [38] Stepanov ND, Yurchenko NY, Shaysultanov DG, Salishchev GA, Tikhonovsky MA. Effect of Al on structure and mechanical properties of Al_xNbTiVZr ($x = 0, 0.5, 1, 1.5$) high entropy alloys. *Mater Sci Technol* 2015;31(10):1184–1193. doi: 10.1179/1743284715Y.0000000032.
- [39] Li X, Li H, Li Q, Jin C, Hua K, Wang H. The determining role of Al addition on tribology properties and oxidation behavior at elevated temperatures of TiZrHfNb refractory high-entropy alloy. *Mater Charact* 2022;189:111921. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matchar.2022.111921>.
- [40] Li H, Li X, Jin C, Li Q, Ma Q, Wang H, Liu W, Mechanical and tribological performance of AlCr_{0.5}NbTa_xTi_{1-x} ($x = 0, 0.5, 1$) refractory high-entropy alloys. *J Mater Sci Technol* 2023;156:241–253. doi: 10.1016/j.jmst.2023.02.016.
- [41] Xu ZQ, Ma ZL, Wang M, Chen YW, Tan YD, Cheng XW. Design of novel low-density refractory high entropy alloys for high-temperature applications. *Mater Sci Eng A* 2019;755:318–22. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.msea.2019.03.054>.
- [42] Gorr B, Mueller F, Christ HJ, Mueller T, Chen H, Kauffmann A, et al. High temperature oxidation behavior of an equimolar refractory metal-based alloy 20Nb20Mo20Cr20Ti20Al with and without Si addition. *J Alloys Compd* 2016; 688:468–77. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2016.07.219>.
- [43] Müller F, Gorr B, Christ HJ, Chen H, Kauffmann A, Heilmaier M. Effect of microalloying with silicon on high temperature oxidation resistance of novel refractory high-entropy alloy Ta-Mo-Cr-Ti-Al. *Mater High Temp* 2018;35(1–3): 168–76. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09603409.2017.1389115>.
- [44] Gorr B, Azim M, Christ HJ, Mueller T, Schliephake D, Heilmaier M. Phase equilibria, microstructure, and high temperature oxidation resistance of novel refractory high-entropy alloys. *J Alloys Compd* 2015;624:270–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2014.11.012>.
- [45] Jeong H-I, Lee C-M, Kim D-H. Manufacturing of Ti-Nb-Cr-V-Ni-Al Refractory High-Entropy Alloys Using Direct Energy Deposition. *Materials* 2022. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma15196570>.
- [46] Yang J, Zhou Y, Zhang Y, Chen G. Solid solution formation criteria in the multi-component alloys with high entropy of mixing. *Chin Mater Sci Technol Equip* 2007;5:61–3.
- [47] Miller M, Liaw P. *Bulk Metallic Glasses: an Overview* 2007.
- [48] Senkov ON, Couzinie JP, Rao SI, Soni V, Banerjee R. Temperature dependent deformation behavior and strengthening mechanisms in a low density refractory high entropy alloy Al₁₀Nb₁₅Ta₅Ti₃₀Zr₄₀. *Materialia* 2020;9:100627. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mtla.2020.100627>.
- [49] Ley NA, Segovia S, Gorsse S, Young ML. Characterization and modeling of NbNiTaTiW and NbNiTaTiW-Al refractory high-entropy alloys. *Metall Mater Trans A* 2019;50:4867–76. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11661-019-05384-w>.
- [50] Poletti MG, Fiore G, Szost BA, Battezzati L. Search for high entropy alloys in the X-NbTaTiZr systems (X=Al, Cr, V, Sn). *J Alloys Compd* 2015;620:283–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2014.09.145>.
- [51] Stepanov ND, Shaysultanov DG, Salishchev GA, Tikhonovsky MA. Structure and mechanical properties of a light-weight AlNbTiV high entropy alloy. *Mater Lett* 2015;142:153–5. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matlet.2014.11.162>.
- [52] Stepanov ND, Yurchenko NY, Sokolovsky VS, Tikhonovsky MA, Salishchev GA. An AlNbTiVZr_{0.5} high-entropy alloy combining high specific strength and good ductility. *Mater Lett* 2015;161:136–9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matlet.2015.08.099>.
- [53] Jayaraj J, Thirathipviwat P, Han J, Gebert A. Microstructure, mechanical and thermal oxidation behavior of AlNbTiZr high entropy alloy. *Intermetallics* 2018; 100:9–19. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intermet.2018.05.015>.
- [54] Gao XJ, Wang L, Guo NN, Luo LS, Zhu GM, Shi CC, et al. Microstructure characteristics and mechanical properties of Hf_{0.5}Mo_{0.5}NbTiZr refractory high entropy alloy with Cr addition. *Int J Refract Met Hard Mater* 2021;95:105405. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijrmhm.2020.105405>.
- [55] Fang L, Wang J, Li X, Tao X, Ouyang Y, Du Y. Effect of Cr content on microstructure characteristics and mechanical properties of ZrNbTaHf_{0.2}Cr_x refractory high entropy alloy. *J Alloys Compd* 2022;924:166593. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2022.166593>.
- [56] Zhang B, Gao MC, Zhang Y, Guo SM. Senary refractory high-entropy alloy Cr_xMoNbTaVW. *Calphad* 2015;51:193–201. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.calphad.2015.09.007>.
- [57] Gao MC, Carney CS, Doğan ÖN, Jablonksi PD, Hawk JA, Alman DE. Design of Refractory High-Entropy Alloys. *JOM* 2015;67(11):2653–69. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11837-015-1617-z>.
- [58] Gong W, He Y, Kuang W, Qian J, Wu L, Xiao Y, et al. Microstructure and oxidation behavior of the CrMoNbTaV high-entropy alloy. *J Mater Res* 2019;34(2):301–8. <https://doi.org/10.1557/jmr.2018.340>.
- [59] Tong Y, Bai L, Liang X, Chen Y, Zhang Z, Liu J, et al. Influence of alloying elements on mechanical and electronic properties of NbMoTaWx (X = Cr, Zr, V, Hf and Re) refractory high entropy alloys. *Intermetallics* 2020;126:106928. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intermet.2020.106928>.
- [60] Coury FG, Butler T, Chaput K, Saville A, Copley J, Foltz J, et al. Phase equilibria, mechanical properties and design of quaternary refractory high entropy alloys. *Mater Des* 2018;155:244–56. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matdes.2018.06.003>.
- [61] Ikeuchi D, King DJM, Laws KJ, Knowles AJ, Aughterson RD, Lumpkin GR, et al. Cr-Mo-V-W: a new refractory and transition metal high-entropy alloy system. *Scrip Mater* 2019;158:141–5. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scriptamat.2018.08.045>.
- [62] Yi J, Yang L, Wang L, Xu M. Lightweight, refractory high-entropy alloy, CrNbTa_{0.25}TiZr, with high yield strength. *Met Mater Int* 2022;28(2):448–55. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12540-021-01059-7>.
- [63] Senkov ON, Senkova SV, Woodward C, Miracle DB. Low-density, refractory multi-principal element alloys of the Cr-Nb-Ti-V-Zr system: microstructure and phase analysis. *Acta Mater* 2013;61(5):1545–57. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actamat.2012.11.032>.
- [64] Andreoli AF, Mendes RG, Witusiewicz VT, Shuleshova O, van Huis MA, Nielsch K, et al. Phase constitution and microstructure of the NbTiVZr refractory high-entropy alloy solidified upon different processing. *Acta Mater* 2021;221:117416. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actamat.2021.117416>.

- [65] Kareer A, Waite JC, Li B, Couet A, Armstrong DEJ, Wilkinson AJ. Short communication: 'low activation, refractory, high entropy alloys for nuclear applications'. *J Nucl Mater* 2019;526:151744. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnucmat.2019.151744>.
- [66] Ma L, Wang L, Zhang T, Inoue A. Bulk glass formation of Ti-Zr-Hf-Cu-M (M = Fe, Co, Ni) Alloys. *Mater Trans* 2002;43(2):277–80. <https://doi.org/10.2320/matertrans.43.277>.
- [67] Plummer J, Cunliffe A, Figueroa A. Glass formation in a high entropy alloy, presentation at the 8th international conference on bulk metallic glasses. Hong Kong 2011. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-27013-5_13.
- [68] Wu S, Qiao D, Zhang H, Miao J, Zhao H, Wang J, et al. Microstructure and mechanical properties of $C_xHf_{0.25}NbTaW_{0.5}$ refractory high-entropy alloys at room and high temperatures. *J Mater Sci Technol* 2022;97:229–38. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmst.2021.05.015>.
- [69] Sheikh S, Shafeie S, Hu Q, Ahlström J, Persson C, Veselý J, et al. Alloy design for intrinsically ductile refractory high-entropy alloys. *J Appl Phys* 2016;120(16):164902. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4966659>.
- [70] Iijima Y, Nagase T, Matsugaki A, Wang P, Ameyama K, Nakano T. Design and development of Ti-Zr-Hf-Nb-Ta-Mo high-entropy alloys for metallic biomaterials. *Mater Des* 2021;202:109548. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matdes.2021.109548>.
- [71] Huang W, Hou J, Wang X, Qiao J, Wu Y. Excellent room-temperature tensile ductility in as-cast $Ti_{37}V_{15}Nb_{22}Hf_{23}W_3$ refractory high entropy alloys. *Intermetallics* 2022;151:107735. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intermet.2022.107735>.
- [72] Zhang C, MacDonald BE, Guo F, Wang H, Zhu C, Liu X, et al. Cold-workable refractory complex concentrated alloys with tunable microstructure and good room-temperature tensile behavior. *Scr Mater* 2020;188:16–20. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scriptamat.2020.07.006>.
- [73] Juan CC, Tseng KK, Hsu WL, Tsai MH, Tsai CW, Lin CM, et al. Solution strengthening of ductile refractory $HfMo_xNbTaTiZr$ high-entropy alloys. *Mater Lett* 2016;175:284–7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matlet.2016.03.133>.
- [74] Yang C, Bian H, Aoyagi K, Hayasaka Y, Yamanaka K, Chiba A. Synergetic strengthening in $HfMoNbTaTi$ refractory high-entropy alloy via disordered nanoscale phase and semicoherent refractory particle. *Mater Des* 2021;212:110248. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matdes.2021.110248>.
- [75] Wang M, Ma Z, Xu Z, Cheng X. Microstructures and mechanical properties of $HfNbTaTiZrW$ and $HfNbTaTiZrMoW$ refractory high-entropy alloys. *J Alloys Compd* 2019;803:778–85. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2019.06.138>.
- [76] Juan CC, Tsai MH, Tsai CW, Lin CM, Wang WR, Yang CC, et al. Enhanced mechanical properties of $HfMoNbTaTiZr$ and $HfMoNbTaTiZr$ refractory high-entropy alloys. *Intermetallics* 2015;62:76–83. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intermet.2015.03.013>.
- [77] Guo NN, Wang L, Luo LS, Li XZ, Su YQ, Guo JJ, et al. Microstructure and mechanical properties of refractory $MoNbHfZrTi$ high-entropy alloy. *Mater Des* 2015;81:87–94. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matdes.2015.05.019>.
- [78] Lilienst L, Couzinié JP, Perrière L, Bourgon J, Emery N, Guillot I. New structure in refractory high-entropy alloys. *Mater Lett* 2014;132:123–5. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matlet.2014.06.064>.
- [79] An Z, Mao S, Liu Y, Wang L, Zhou H, Gan B, et al. A novel $HfNbTaTiV$ high-entropy alloy of superior mechanical properties designed on the principle of maximum lattice distortion. *J Mater Sci Technol* 2021;79:109–17. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmst.2020.10.073>.
- [80] Gao MC, Zhang B, Yang S, Guo SM. Senary refractory high-entropy alloy $HfNbTaTiVZr$. *Metall Mater Trans A* 2016;47(7):3333–45. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11661-015-3105-z>.
- [81] Senkov ON, Scott JM, Senkova SV, Miracle DB, Woodward CF. Microstructure and room temperature properties of a high-entropy $TaNbHfZrTi$ alloy. *J Alloys Compd* 2011;509(20):6043–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2011.02.171>.
- [82] Fazakas É, Zadorozhnyy V, Varga LK, Inoue A, Louzguine-Luzgin DV, Tian F, et al. Experimental and theoretical study of $Ti_{20}Zr_{20}Hf_{20}Nb_{20}X_{20}$ (X = V or Cr) refractory high-entropy alloys. *Int J Refract Met Hard Mater* 2014;47:131–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijrmhm.2014.07.009>.
- [83] Jin C, Li X, Kang J, Li H, Wang H. Effect of interstitial oxygen/nitrogen on mechanical and wear properties of $TiZrHfNb$ refractory high-entropy alloy. *J Alloys Compd* 2023;960:170863. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2023.170863>.
- [84] Li T, Lu Y, Li Z, Wang T, Li T. Hot deformation behavior and microstructure evolution of non-equimolar $Ti_2ZrHfV_{0.5}Ta_{0.2}$ refractory high-entropy alloy. *Intermetallics* 2022;146:107586. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intermet.2022.107586>.
- [85] Wang SP, Xu J. (TiZrNbTa)-Mo high-entropy alloys: Dependence of microstructure and mechanical properties on Mo concentration and modeling of solid solution strengthening. *Intermetallics* 2018;95:59–72. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intermet.2018.01.017>.
- [86] Wei W, Wang T, Wang C, Wu M, Nie Y, Peng J. Ductile $W_{0.4}MoNb_2TaTi$ refractory high-entropy alloys with excellent elevated temperature strength. *Mater Lett* 2021;295:129753. doi: 10.1016/j.matlet.2021.129753.
- [87] Zheng W, Lü S, Wu S, Chen X, Guo W. Development of $MoNbVTa_x$ refractory high entropy alloy with high strength at elevated temperature. *Mater Sci Eng A* 2022;850:143554. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.msea.2022.143554>.
- [88] Han ZD, Luan HW, Liu X, Chen N, Li XY, Shao Y, et al. Microstructures and mechanical properties of $Ti_xNbMoTaW$ refractory high-entropy alloys. *Mater Sci Eng A* 2018;712:380–5. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.msea.2017.12.004>.
- [89] Hua N, Wang W, Wang Q, Ye Y, Lin S, Zhang L, et al. Mechanical, corrosion, and wear properties of biomedical Ti-Zr-Nb-Ta-Mo high entropy alloys. *J Alloys Compd* 2021;861:157997. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2020.157997>.
- [90] Yao HW, Qiao JW, Hawk JA, Zhou HF, Chen MW, Gao MC. Mechanical properties of refractory high-entropy alloys: experiments and modeling. *J Alloys Compd* 2017;696:1139–50. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2016.11.188>.
- [91] Zhang B, Gao MC, Zhang Y, Yang S, Guo SM. Senary refractory high entropy alloy $MoNbTaTiVW$. *Mater Sci Technol* 2015;31(10):1207–13. <https://doi.org/10.1179/1743284715Y.0000000031>.
- [92] Duan C, Reiberg M, Kutlesa P, Li X, Pippan R, Werner E. Strain-hardening properties of the high-entropy alloy $MoNbTaTiVZr$ processed by high-pressure torsion. *Contin Mech Thermodyn* 2022;34(2):475–89. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00161-021-01065-5>.
- [93] Yao H, Qiao JW, Gao MC, Hawk JA, Ma SG, Zhou H. $MoNbTaV$ medium-entropy alloy. *Entropy* 2016. <https://doi.org/10.3390/e18050189>.
- [94] Wang M, Ma ZL, Xu ZQ, Cheng XW. Designing $V_xNbMoTa$ refractory high-entropy alloys with improved properties for high-temperature applications. *Scr Mater* 2021;191:131–6. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scriptamat.2020.09.027>.
- [95] Senkov ON, Wilks GB, Miracle DB, Chuang CP, Liaw PK. Refractory high-entropy alloys. *Intermetallics* 2010;18(9):1758–65. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intermet.2010.05.014>.
- [96] Chen SH, Zhang JS, Guan S, Li T, Liu JQ, Wu FF, Wu YC. Microstructure and mechanical properties of $WNbMoTaZr_x$ ($x = 0.1, 0.3, 0.5, 1.0$) refractory high entropy alloys. *Mater Sci Eng A* 2022;835:142701. doi: 10.1016/j.msea.2022.142701.
- [97] Chen SY, Yang X, Dahmen KA, Liaw PK, Zhang Y. Microstructures and cracking noise of $Al_xNbTiMoV$ high entropy alloys. *Entropy* 2014;870–84. <https://doi.org/10.3390/e16020870>.
- [98] Zhang Y, Yang X, Liaw PK. Alloy design and properties optimization of high-entropy alloys. *JOM* 2012;64(7):830–8. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11837-012-0366-5>.
- [99] Anzorena MS, Bertolo AA, Galletti L, Kreiner AJ, Mosca HO, Bozzolo G, et al. Characterization and modeling of a $MoTaVWZr$ high entropy alloy. *Mater Des* 2016;111:382–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matdes.2016.09.006>.
- [100] Montero J, Ek G, Laversenne L, Nassif V, Zepon G, Sahlberg M, et al. Hydrogen storage properties of the refractory Ti-V-Zr-Nb-Ta multi-principal element alloy. *J Alloys Compd* 2020;835:155376. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2020.155376>.
- [101] Pei X, Du Y, Wang H, Hu M, Wang H, Liu W. Investigation of high temperature tribological performance of $TiZrV_{0.5}Nb_{0.5}$ refractory high-entropy alloy optimized by Si microalloying. *Tribol Int* 2022;176:107885. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.triboint.2022.107885>.
- [102] Lin CM, Juan CC, Chang CH, Tsai CW, Yeh JW. Effect of Al addition on mechanical properties and microstructure of refractory $Al_xHfNbTaTiZr$ alloys. *J Alloys Compd* 2015;624:100–7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2014.11.064>.
- [103] Senkov ON, Senkova SV, Woodward C. Effect of aluminum on the microstructure and properties of two refractory high-entropy alloys. *Acta Mater* 2014;68:214–28. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actamat.2014.01.029>.
- [104] Singh AK, Subramaniam A. On the formation of disordered solid solutions in multi-component alloys. *J Alloys Compd* 2014;587:113–9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2013.10.133>.
- [105] Toda-Caraballo I, Rivera-Díaz-del-Castillo PEJ. A criterion for the formation of high entropy alloys based on lattice distortion. *Intermetallics* 2016;71:76–87. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intermet.2015.12.011>.
- [106] Adachi H, Mukoyama T, Kawai J. Hartree-Fock-Slater method for materials science: the DV-X Alpha method for design and characterization of materials. Springer; 2006.
- [107] Yoshihisa M, Masahiko M, Tomonori N, Takashi S. Alloying effects on the electronic structure of chromium. *J Phys: Condens Matter* 1996;8(20):3619. <https://doi.org/10.1088/0953-8984/8/20/008>.
- [108] Sheikh S, Klement U, Guo S. Predicting the solid solubility limit in high-entropy alloys using the molecular orbital approach. *J Appl Phys* 2015;118(19):194902. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4935620>.
- [109] Morinaga M, Yukawa N, Adachi H. Alloying effect on the electronic structure of $Ni_3Al(\gamma)$. *J Phys Soc Jpn* 1984;53(2):653–63. <https://doi.org/10.1143/JPSJ.53.653>.
- [110] Zhang Y, Zuo TT, Tang Z, Gao MC, Dahmen KA, Liaw PK, et al. Microstructures and properties of high-entropy alloys. *Prog Mater Sci* 2014;61:1–93. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pmatsci.2013.10.001>.
- [111] Gan GY, Ma L, Luo DM, Jiang S, Tang BY. Influence of Al substitution for Sc on thermodynamic properties of HCP high entropy alloy $Hf_{0.25}Ti_{0.25}Zr_{0.25}Sc_{0.25-x}Al_x$ from first-principles investigation. *Phys B* 2020;593:412272. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.physb.2020.412272>.
- [112] Shao L, Yang M, Ma L, Tang BY. Effect of Ta and Ti content on high temperature elasticity of $HfNbZrTa_{1-x}Ti_x$ refractory high-entropy alloys. *Int J Refract Met Hard Mater* 2021;95:105451. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijrmhm.2020.105451>.
- [113] Yan X, Liaw PK, Zhang Y. Ultrastrong and ductile BCC high-entropy alloys with low-density via dislocation regulation and nanoprecipitates. *J Mater Sci Technol* 2021;95:109–16. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmst.2021.08.034>.
- [114] Mishra SS, Yadav TP, Srivastava ON, Mukhopadhyay NK, Biswas K. Formation and stability of C14 type Laves phase in multi component high-entropy alloys. *J Alloys Compd* 2020;832:153764. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2020.153764>.
- [115] Guo S, Hu Q, Ng C, Liu CT. More than entropy in high-entropy alloys: forming solid solutions or amorphous phase. *Intermetallics* 2013;41:96–103. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intermet.2013.05.002>.

- [116] Niessen AK, de Boer FR, Boom R, de Châtel PF, Mattens WCM, Miedema AR. Model predictions for the enthalpy of formation of transition metal alloys II. *Calphad* 1983;7(1):51–70. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0364-5916\(83\)90030-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0364-5916(83)90030-5).
- [117] Guo S, Liu CT. Phase stability in high entropy alloys: Formation of solid-solution phase or amorphous phase. *Prog Nat Sci: Mater Int* 2011;21(6):433–46. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1002-0071\(12\)60080-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1002-0071(12)60080-X).
- [118] Feng R, Gao MC, Lee C, Mathes M, Zuo T, Chen S, et al. Design of light-weight high-entropy alloys. *Entropy* 2016. <https://doi.org/10.3390/e18090333>.
- [119] Egami T, Waseda Y. Atomic size effect on the formability of metallic glasses. *J Non-Cryst Solids* 1984;64(1):113–34. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-3093\(84\)90210-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-3093(84)90210-2).
- [120] Senkov ON, Miracle DB. A new thermodynamic parameter to predict formation of solid solution or intermetallic phases in high entropy alloys. *J Alloys Compd* 2016;658:603–7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2015.10.279>.
- [121] Wang Z, Huang Y, Yang Y, Wang J, Liu CT. Atomic-size effect and solid solubility of multicomponent alloys. *Scr Mater* 2015;94:28–31. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scriptamat.2014.09.010>.
- [122] Singh AK, Kumar N, Dwivedi A, Subramaniam A. A geometrical parameter for the formation of disordered solid solutions in multi-component alloys. *Intermetallics* 2014;53:112–9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intermet.2014.04.019>.
- [123] Fang S, Xiao X, Xia L, Li W, Dong Y. Relationship between the widths of supercooled liquid regions and bond parameters of Mg-based bulk metallic glasses. *J Non-Cryst Solids* 2003;321(1–2):120–5. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-3093\(03\)00155-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-3093(03)00155-8).
- [124] Ye YF, Wang Q, Lu J, Liu CT, Yang Y. Design of high entropy alloys: a single-parameter thermodynamic rule. *Scr Mater* 2015;104:53–5. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scriptamat.2015.03.023>.
- [125] Tong CJ, Chen YL, Yeh JW, Lin SJ, Chen SK, Shun TT, et al. Microstructure characterization of $\text{Al}_x\text{CoCrCuFeNi}$ high-entropy alloy system with multiprincipal elements. *Metall Mater Trans A* 2005;36(4):881–93. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11661-005-0283-0>.
- [126] Guo NN, Wang L, Luo LS, Li XZ, Chen RR, Su YQ, et al. Microstructure and mechanical properties of refractory high entropy (Mo_{0.5}NbHf_{0.5}ZrTi)BCC/M₅Si₃ in-situ compound. *J Alloys Compd* 2016;660:197–203. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2015.11.091>.
- [127] Takeuchi A, Inoue A. Mixing enthalpy of liquid phase calculated by miedema's scheme and approximated with sub-regular solution model for assessing forming ability of amorphous and glassy alloys. *Intermetallics* 2010;18(9):1779–89. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intermet.2010.06.003>.
- [128] Takeuchi A, Inoue A. Classification of bulk metallic glasses by atomic size difference, heat of mixing and period of constituent elements and its application to characterization of the main alloying element. *Mater Trans* 2005;46(12):2817–29. <https://doi.org/10.2320/matertrans.46.2817>.
- [129] Tang Z, Gao MC, Diao H, Yang T, Liu J, Zuo T, et al. Aluminum alloying effects on lattice types, microstructures, and mechanical behavior of high-entropy alloys systems. *Jom* 2013;65:1848–58. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11837-013-0776-z>.